

ANALYSIS OF FORENSIC MEDICAL EXAMINATION OF INJURIES ON "DAMAS" CARS

Khakimov Zaynobiddin Kabiljonovich

senior lecturer of the Department of Pathological Anatomy and Forensic
Medicine, Andijan State Medical Institute

Imomov Khojiakbar Makhamadalievich

assistant of the Department of Pathological physiology and Pathological
anatomy, Fergana Medical Institute of Public Health

Summary: this article examined the materials of 49 corpses and 812 living person injured in car accidents in Damas, which were investigated by forensic medical examination in 2022/2023.

The mechanism of damage development occurred with the movement of the body from rear to front. The drivers injuries et passengers were observed in the form of abrasions and bruises to the forehead, face, chest, abdomen, arms and legs.

Keywords: "Damas", car, automobile accident, driver, passengers, injuries, abrasions, bruises.

Relevance: in October 2021, a presentation was held in Geneva of the World Health Organization's global social Company "ten years of action to ensure road safety in 2021-2030". The stated goal is to reduce fatalities and injuries by road traffic accidents by at least 50 percent by 2030.

Road accidents can cause another 13 million deaths and 500 million injuries over the next decade. This is especially fraught with countries with a low population and an average income. Well, one of the main causes of premature death all over the world remains precisely road accidents.

"Traffic accidents in the form of disability, kulfat, suffering, financial loss and various other frustrations endlessly destroy families, communities, society, the health

system, in general, all of humanity,” said Who CEO Tedros Adhanom Gebreyesus. By making roads and vehicles more secure, enhancing pedestrian crossings, cycling safety, and promoting infrastructure development, such calamities can be greatly reduced. The Global decade plan is an effort to ensure road safety. This document reflects the specific steps that all countries and the community must take”¹.

Injuries to drivers and front, rear seat passengers in car interior trauma have not been sufficiently studied, the mechanism of their occurrence, the frequency of occurrence and the study of the characteristics of these injuries are also important for judicial authorities and forensic medical experts [2, 3].

The purpose of the study: to study the nature of injuries to the body of rowers who were on the steering wheel in damage to the cabin of the “Damas” car and sat in the front, rear seats.

Research materials and methods: archival materials of 49 corpses and 812 living persons who died in car accidents in 2022/2023 in the Andijan branch of the scientific and practical center of Forensic Medicine examination of the Republic (forensic medical conclusions, photoilovas, forensic histological examination materials). The results from the study were analyzed according to the statistical method.

Differences are seen in the interior design of the car»Damas» - in the interior of the salon-constructive features, the relatively high location of the steering column, the relatively steep location of the front dashboard-70-80°, the high location of the seats, etc. These discrepancies demonstrate the specificity of injuries that occur during a car accident.

The study studied injuries in the body tissues of drivers and passengers who were injured in the "Damas" car (861). In the observations, 1/4 cars collided with each other, 2/4 cars crashed into roadside barriers, and 1/4 cars overturned.

¹ https://uza.uz/uz/posts/dunyoda-yol-transport-halokatlari-muammosi_368183
WWW.HUMOSCIENCE.COM

Results of the research: in a car accident on the "Damas" car, it was observed that the movement of the body from back to front caused many accidents. About 17% of drivers were found to have joint injuries to the cranium and thorax, abdominal organs, close to 35% of drivers had closed chest injuries, heart sacs, heart and lung rupture deaths. In front seat passengers, however, these were seen to be the result of close to 19% open cranial injury, close to 30% closed cranial injury, joint chest and abdominal limb injuries, close to 17% closed chest injury, rupture of the pulmonary artery, acute internal bleeding. In the middle and back seat passengers, however, these were seen to be the result of close to 5% closed cranial injury, joint chest and abdominal limb injuries and close to 3% closed chest injuries.

Diagram-1

Features of injuries inside the salon in the car "Damas"

In drivers inside the "Damas" car, injuries are mainly from the left side, in the forehead-upper area - about 80%, and on the left cheek - about 17%, around the left eyelids - about 37%, in the nose area - about 24%, on the lower surface of the chest area of the forehead - about 70%, in the left shoulder area - about 24%, on the outer surface of the thigh area - about 47%, abrasions, bruises and wounds were recorded.

Injuries to passengers in the front seat are mainly from the right side, the forehead area is about 57% in the middle of the front surface, and in the eyebrow area - about 12%, in the abdominal area - about 35%, in the waist area - about 45%, in the upper area of the right elbow - about 45%, and in the upper area of the right Injuries to passengers in the back seat were left and right, respectively, in the forehead-top Sox - about 12%, in the cheek - about 8%, in the area of the upper and lower lip - about 7%, on the front surface of the chest - about 6%, in the shoulder area-about 7% abrasions, bruises were observed.

Diagram-2

Features of bodily injuries inside the salon in the car "Damas"

"Damas" cars received the same shape as noted in the literature [4] oblong - rhombic (70%) in drivers; bumps and bruises in injuries inside the salon, passengers were noted to have an oblong - oval shape (80%) .

In the drivers of the "Damas" car, the bleeds were 0.5-6.5 cm in the head and face, chest, limb areas, the bumps were 1-8 cm in the head, face, neck and groin area, chest and limbs, and the wounds were 0.5-5 cm in the head and face, neck and limb areas.

The results were as follows when comparing the dimensions of injuries in the passengers of the "Damas" car by body area.

In passenger persons injured in the car "Damas", the bleeds amounted to 0.5-6.5 cm in the head and face, chest, abdomen and waist areas, and wounds in the limb areas-

0.5-6.5 cm in the head, face, abdomen and waist area, and 0.4-5cm in the limbs, 1-5.6 cm in the head and face, limb areas.

Conclusion: injuries to the chest were recorded in 22% of cases in the drivers of the Damas car in combination with severe degree injuries to other members. In the car "Damas", it was seen that about 17-35% of drivers in the back-to - Front movement of the body suffered joint injuries to the head and chest, abdominal organs, and in passengers in the front seat-up to 19-30%, in passengers in the rear seats-2-5%.

In drivers inside the "Damas" car, injuries were mostly left-handed, up to 80% in upper-body members, 30-47% in lower-body members, and in front-seat passengers, injuries were mostly right-handed, up to 57% in upper-body members, 45% in lower-body members, and in rear-seat passengers, these were left-or right-sided 12% and 7%, respectively.

Cars "Damas" in the injuries inside the salon, the abrasions and bruises on the drivers took on a oblong – rhombic shape, on passengers - on the abrasions and bruises -on the oblong – oval shape.

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